

Identifying Predatory Journals Cheat Sheet

Indexation in Databases

- ❑ International Standard Serial Number ([ISSN](https://portal.issn.org/))
 - ❑ <https://portal.issn.org/>
- ❑ Directory of Open Access Journals ([DOAJ](https://www.doaj.org/))
 - ❑ <https://www.doaj.org/>
- ❑ SCOPUS >> [CITESCORE](https://www.scopus.com/sources)
 - ❑ <https://www.scopus.com/sources>
- ❑ Web of Science (WOS) >> [Impact Factor](https://mjl.clarivate.com/home)
 - ❑ <https://mjl.clarivate.com/home>

Red Flags

- ❑ Advertises fake/wrong Impact Factor or indexation in databases
- ❑ APC charges are not disclosed
- ❑ Unclear publisher location, contact details
- ❑ Peer-Review process is not explained/detailed
- ❑ Articles out of scope and/or of dubious quality (authors mostly from one country)
- ❑ Check the Editorial Board! Expertise, affiliation, Editor in Chief

Orange Flags

- ❑ Mimics name or similar website of other known journals
- ❑ Need to pay to withdraw the article
- ❑ Targets authors aggressively via email and (+ grammatical errors)
- ❑ Not member of [Committee on Publication and Ethics](#) (COPE)
- ❑ Not member of [Open Access Scholarly Publishers Association](#) (OASPA)
- ❑ Extremely high / suspicious number of published papers per month

How to use:

This cheat sheet was designed to guide researchers on how to assess the quality of a scientific journal. A journal should have an ISSN number and ideally, it should be indexed either in SCOPUS and/or Web of Science (WOS) (See yellow box under Indexation of Databases). For Open Access journals, the journal should also be indexed in the Directory for Open Access Journals (DOAJ). The information available in the "Red flags" section strongly correlates with predatory journals. The "Orange flags section" describes questionable practices strongly discouraged or which can affect the quality of the peer-review process.

Checks carried out		DOAJ	SCOPUS	WOS
ISSN number	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Journal Title	No	No	No	Yes
Journal Publisher	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Journal website (online journals)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Provides access to all the content of the journal	Not applicable	Yes	Yes	Yes
Presence of Peer review policy	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Contact details	Yes	No	No	Yes
Scholarly content	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Article titles and article abstracts in English	No	No	Yes	Yes
Bibliographic information on Roman script	No	No	No	Yes
Clarity of language	No	No	Yes	Yes
Timelines and/or publication volume	No	No	Yes	Yes
Website functionality/Journal format	Yes	No	No	Yes
Presence of Ethics statements	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes
Editorial affiliation details	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Author affiliation details	No	No	No	Yes
Editorial board composition	Minimum	Yes	Yes	Yes
Validity of statements	Unclear	Yes	Yes	Yes
Peer review	No	No	Yes	Yes
Content relevance	No	No	Yes	Yes
Grant support details	No	No	No	Yes
Adherence to community standards	No	No	No	Yes
Author distribution	No	No	No	Yes
Appropriate citations to the literature	No	No	Yes	Yes
Comparative citation analysis	No	No	Yes	Yes
Author citation analysis	No	No	Yes	Yes
Editorial Board Citation Analysis	No	No	No	Yes
Content Significance	No	No	Yes	Yes
Journal needs to have published a minimum of iter	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Open Access checks	Yes	Yes	No	No
Advertisement checks	Yes	Yes	No	No
Special Issues rules	Yes	Yes	No	No
Licensing and copyrights	Yes	Yes	No	No
APC statements	Yes	Yes	No	No
Extra checks depending on the type of the journal	Yes	Yes	No	No

Overview of the checks performed by each database for a journal to be indexed. Below you can find the link with more information for each database.

Sources

<https://www.doaj.org/apoph/faq/ide/>

<https://www.elsevier.com/products/scopus/content/content-policy-and-selection?trial=true>

<https://comviate.com/products/scientific-and-academic-research/research-discovery-and-workflow-solutions/web/science-platform/web-of-science-core-collection/editorial-selection-process/editorial-selection-process/>